

Performance-Based Assessment: Reinforcement Learning Models and zStock

Market Volatility

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Abstract

This study presents a comparative evaluation using risk-adjusted metrics of performances among various reinforcement learning algorithms – Q-learning, Deep Q-Networks (DQN), and Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) (Schulman et al.) models. Stock price data for market structures including AAPL, MSFT, and SPY covering the time period from January 1, 2012 until June 1, 2014 were used in the study, while each algorithm had been comprehensively trained, taking into account of various evaluation metrics including Sharpe and Sortino ratios, maximum drawdown, total return, and number of trades. The results had indicated that the Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) agent had outperformed the two supplemental algorithms in terms of overall profitability. Across a majority of the evaluated metrics and stocks, the Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) agent consistently outperformed both the DQN and Q-learning regarding general profitability. However, there is a narrow range of market structures alongside stocks within the program, possibly inhibiting more concrete results.

Keywords: Reinforcement learning; stock market volatility; risk-adjusted returns; Q-learning; Proximal Policy Optimization; Deep-Q-Network.

Introduction

Over recent years, stock market volatility has risen sharply, increasing investors' need for reliable market analysis sources. Consequently, many institutions have developed forms of market prediction that use machine learning and artificial intelligence. These tools have been integrated into new business ventures to provide market analysis and potentially boost institutional profits. Reinforcement learning is a form of artificial intelligence that assimilates data, while creating outputs and developing decision-making processes; this being derived through the provision of “feedback” regarding past decisions, (Saberironaghi et al). Specifically, this study examines different algorithms, including Q-learning, Deep Q-Networks (DQN), and Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO), and explores how these efficient algorithms were developed and used for significant financial gains. With its policy gradient optimization approach, the PPO model is expected to produce the highest quality results compared to the other two models, (Schulman et al.) This study compares various reinforcement learning algorithms to identify which model performs best in market prediction. There are various different evaluation metrics that will be measured when determining the success of each agent; factors including, Sharpe and Sortino ratios, MaxDrawdown, TotalReturn, among others.

Literature review

The constraints and upsides among all reinforcement learning algorithms have been assessed. Through comprehensive research, it became evident that Q-learning agents are programmed to essentially “analyze” market structures; the reason is rooted in the agent's purpose. Q-learning is a popular reinforcement learning tool, as the software identifies positive and negative actions, and updates its policies, enhancing the agent’s judgment. However, when integrated with neural networks, the agent’s judgment had become unstable, providing flawed results. (Saberironaghi et al.), This issue had been addressed with the usage of a DQN agent. Evidence suggests “DQN integrate CNNs with Q-learning, enabling the handling of high-dimensional and complex data while mitigating instability issues caused by the agents typically overproject specific “choices”, thus having a direct correlation to flawed data results. This being a result of the deteriorating performance showcased through the agent’s choices. It became evident that, “We propose a specific adaptation to the DQN algorithm and show that the resulting algorithm not only reduces the observed overestimations, as hypothesized, but that this also leads to much better performance on several games” (Van Hasselt, Guez, & Silver, 2016, p. 2095). Prior research argues that Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) agents have been classified as effective algorithms within dynamic environments, including stock market volatility. In the provided study, the PPO agent was consolidated with neural networks, developing the agent’s understanding of data analysis. Referencing each dataset, the agent was trained by analyzing critical stock market data. Specific data within this study were collected from companies including NVIDIA, Apple, Microsoft, Google, and Amazon, spanning the previously highlighted timeframe. The combination of the PPO agent with neural networks ensured that the agent had effectively produced reliable results. The results were indicative of the agent’s policy creation; the algorithm instructed the agent to “select the most profitable action in each time step” (Sarlakifar et al., 2023). Despite the major growth of reinforcement learning in financial markets, no study has directly compared Q-learning, DQN, and PPO, under identical circumstances and same evaluation metrics. This is a major gap that limits the ability to conclude which algorithm can provide the highest degree of overall profitability. This additionally results in a lack of meaningful synthesis between analysis of each model. Additionally, prior studies had not accounted for metrics such as transaction costs, meaning trading actions had been free of commissions. This study addresses that gap through the training and evaluation of all three models under identical circumstances.

Methods:

Dataset

This study intends to implement a dataset for several companies, imported from Yahoo Finance, including features as open, high, low, close prices, volume, moving averages, relative strength index, moving average convergence divergence, volatility, and a flag to indicate the agent’s status. The state vector presented to the agent at each time step consisted of 10 features including the open price, high, low and close prices, volume, 10-day moving averaged, 50-day moving average, relative strength index (RSI), moving average convergence divergence (MACD), and a position flag that indicates whether the agent currently held a long position. The program simulates an environment in which daily market data was measured from various different stocks, as the agent was provided with various key metrics to inform actions made. The agent was trained on the data through a defined list of actions. The dataset analyzed was provided by Yahoo Finance, and measured various factors of several stocks, including AAPL, MSFT, SPY. Stock. Missing data within the timeframe was not accounted for. The agent has been trained from

1/01/2012 until 6/01/2014. The dataset was divided into a training period spanning January 1, 2012 to December 31, 2013, and a testing period spanning January 1, 2014 to June 1, 2014. The agents had been exclusively trained on the training set. Moving averages were implemented to identify metric trends across several days. In addition, the frequency of the analysis has been collected daily, ensuring reputable data has been assessed. Within the environment, the agent was responsible for observing various factors. This includes analysis of the open price, volume, high, and low price. A minimal amount of data had been filled by using the previous day's values, however, a portion of missing data had not been accounted for, potentially initiating flawed results.

Action Space

Based on the analytics, the agent has three options either to buy, hold, or sell a share of the stock based on data references.

Reward Function

The agent was assessed based on the given reward function: $\text{Reward} = (\text{Change in portfolio value}) - (\text{Transaction cost})$, measuring the differential changes towards the value of the investment portfolio based on past actions. Among the three reinforcement algorithms, both DQN and Proximal Policy Optimization utilize neural networks, whilst Q-learning stores data within a table of actions alongside states, (Chadi and Mousannif). In addition, the hyperparameters within both models utilize gamma, alongside epsilon. However, the Q-learning agent is provided with an Alpha, and action hyperparameter. Whilst the DQN model has a learning rate, epsilon decay, epsilon min, batch size, and memory size hyperparameters. The agents were tested into training and testing periods, provided with the usage of metrics such as total, and average daily return, alongside the Sharpe ratio.

Model Architectures and Hyperparameters

The program was created with the usage of various libraries including TensorFlow, and PyTorch. This study intends to make a clear comparison between three reinforcement learning models, including Q-learning, Deep Q-Networks, and Proximal Policy Optimization. Q-learning agents are instructed to make decisions solely based on decisions made previously, this being achieved through the storage of designated values within a q-table attributing actions to a positive or negative outcome, (Ghasemi et al.) Deep Q-Networks (DQN) highlight a similar idea in correlation to Q-learning, however utilize neural networks as opposed to q-tables, allowing the agent to accurately identify outcomes of actions. In contrast to Deep Q-Networks, alongside Q-learning, Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) agents intend to internalize policies given within a program, with the action of updating policies in miniscule amounts, avoiding major risk factors. (Schulman et al.)

Model Implementation and Frameworks

Within the evaluation, the Q-learning algorithm had been implemented through the Python library associated with NumPy; allowing for increased quality in terms of handling arrays and numerical actions. However the remaining two algorithms had been developed through TensorFlow, allowing for the provision of tools for developing and training neural networks.

Algorithm Overview

1. Q-learning

1. Initialize Q-table with zeros for all state-action pairs.
2. For each episode:
 - a. Observe the current state.
 - b. Choose an action based on an exploration strategy (e.g., epsilon-greedy).
 - c. Take the action, observe the reward and next state.
 - d. Update the Q-value for the state-action pair using the formula:
$$Q(\text{state}, \text{action}) = Q(\text{state}, \text{action}) + \alpha * [\text{reward} + \gamma * \max(\text{Q}(\text{next_state}, \text{all actions})) - Q(\text{state}, \text{action})]$$
 - e. Move to the next state.
3. Repeat until convergence or maximum episodes reached.

2. Deep Q-Network (DQN)

1. Initialize replay memory and neural network with random weights.
2. For each episode:
 - a. Observe the current state.
 - b. Choose an action using an exploration strategy (e.g., epsilon-greedy) based on the neural network's output.
 - c. Execute the action, observe reward and next state.
 - d. Store (state, action, reward, next state) in replay memory.
 - e. Sample a mini-batch of experiences from replay memory.
 - f. Calculate target Q-values using the target network.
 - g. Train the neural network by minimizing the difference between predicted Q-values and target Q-values.
 - h. Periodically update the target network weights.
 - i. Move to the next state.
3. Repeat until convergence or maximum episodes reached.

3. Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO)

1. Initialize policy network with random weights.

2. For each iteration:
 - a. Run the policy in the environment for several steps, collecting states, actions, and rewards.
 - b. Compute advantages and discounted rewards for collected data.
 - c. Update the policy network by maximizing the clipped objective function:
 - This limits how much the policy can change at each update to avoid large policy updates..
 - d. Update value function to predict expected rewards.
3. Repeat for a fixed number of iterations or until performance stabilizes.

Results

Across all three stocks alongside the majority of evaluation metrics, the PPO agent had outperformed both the DQN, and Q-learning models while the DQN model had produced mixed results across stocks, and Q-learning had generally underperformed relative to the other models. When referencing a designated stock market dataset that simulates a multi-stock trading environment consisting of many companies, transformative results were provided. Within the timeframe, the Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) agent provided ideal results, with the highest average Sortino Ratio, CAGR, and various other metrics; this directly supported the initial hypothesis regarding each agent's performance. When assessed on a multitude of different metrics including Sharpe Ratios, Sortino Ratios, Compound Annual Growth, Calmar Ratios, Maximum Drawdowns, Total Returns, Number of Trades, each agent was meticulously observed in regards to performance. For each agent, the standard deviation of each metric was assessed utilizing data from stocks including AAPL, MSFT, and SPY, as shown in Tables 1 and 2.

Discussion

Testing phase metrics provide a clear evaluation regarding the performance of each agent. The initial hypothesis was that Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) could potentially outperform the Q-learning and Deep Q-Network (DQN) models when taking into consideration that PPO models utilize policy gradient optimization. These methods enable the agent to directly update policy networks, with the intent of maximizing trading benefits within the algorithm. The presented results highlight data assessed on a multitude of metrics for stocks including AAPL, MSFT, and SPY. When interpreting the results categorically, they present eye-opening results. For the AAPL stock, the Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) agent expressed higher Sharpe ratios, with a value of ~3.34, while Sortino ratios reached heights of up to ~8.48 (Table 2), indicating superior risk-adjusted returns compared to the DQN and Q-learning agents (Table 1). These results support the conclusion that the Proximal Policy Optimization agent showcased higher quality risk-adjusted returns, compared to the Deep Q-Network (DQN) and Q-learning agents. The Deep Q-Network (DQN) agent's results were relatively mixed between positive and negative outcomes specifically for the Sharpe Ratio metrics. However, when referencing statistics measured on MSFT holdings, all three agents had relatively negative/low Sharpe/Sortino Ratios. Given this statistic, the Proximal Policy Optimization agent was nonetheless able to provide higher-quality results when compared to the other two chosen agents. SPY holdings provided statistics of which the PPO and

Q-learning agents had both performed to a higher degree, in contrast to the Deep Q-Network agent. Across all holdings for stocks, metrics for maximum drawdowns were negative, however the Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) agent had the lowest ratio of losses, while also having the highest degree of total returns, creating more general profit. The Sharpe, Sortino, and Calmar Ratios are numeric based metrics assessing risk-adjusted returns, while the Compound Annual Growth Rate and Total Return indicate the growth of each investment over time. By extension, the Maximum Drawdown metric reflects the largest loss experienced by an agent, while the Number of Trades records how frequently a trade is made by an agent. The presented hypothesis mostly reflects the results accurately. The reason for this can be attributed to the PPO agent's usage of direct updates to strengthen trading strategies. Unlike the Q-learning and DQN agents, PPO agents directly optimize a policy network, preventing large policy updates, which ensures more stable learning across multiple episodes. This study did provide a thorough assessment, however there are many drawbacks that can be presented, including the usage of a limited number of market datasets, specifically focusing on large cap technology stocks. Datasets within this study are from a very narrow timeframe, meaning that very few large economic changes that will incur market volatility will occur, limiting the agent's actions in situations that are considered an imperative. Additionally, This factor creates a limited view of the agent's abilities and will not allow for the encapsulation of the real-world implications of the tool. Future research will be developed by using a larger variety of stocks, along with creating a higher degree of real-world implications in the project. This involves creating an agent that benefits from multiple models, while mitigating individual drawbacks.

Author Notes

In the development of the trading algorithms, AI-assisted tools were utilized to generate and refine portions of the codebase. This approach helped improve coding efficiency and reduce errors while allowing for more focus on the design and analysis aspects of the reinforcement learning models.

Conflicts of Interest

The author declares there are no conflicts of interests related to this work.

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Figure 1: Performance Metrics for DQN and Q-learning Agents

Sharpe	Sortino	CAGR	Calmar	MaxDrawdown	Totalreturn	Ticker	Method	Fold
-2.1761	-2.8657	-0.3992	-1.2462	-0.3203	-0.279	AAPL	DQN	1
2.1659	4.0233	0.5629	8.6048	-0.0654		AAPL	DQN	1
1.6686	0.2122	212	-0.001	0.1092	-0.3342	AAPL	DQN	1
-0.2676	-0.04336	212.2442	-0.5194	-0.1805	-0.0463	AAPL	Q_learning	1
-0.2367	-0.4331		-0.424	-0.1393	-0.0426	MSFT	DQN	1
-0.1604	-0.2036		0.5906	-0.1066	-0.0234	SPY	DQN	1
0.5841	0.8674		1.8497	-0.0573	0.0418	SPY	DQN	1
0.9555	0.7789		1.6922	-0.0472	0.0438	SPY	DQN	1
2.0604	1.9257	0.2276	5.3774	-0.0423	0.1168			
0	0	0	0	0	0	SPY	Q_learning	

Table 2: Performance Metrics for PPO Agent

Sharpe	Sortino	CAGR	Calmar	MaxDrawdown	TotalReturn	Ticker	Fold
3.337	8.4817	1.0022	13.615	-0.0736	0.5319	AAPL	1
-1.5081	-1.3809	-0.2511	-1.4958	-0.1679	-0.149	AAPL	1
-0.162	-0.2983	0.0394	0.2829	-0.1393	-0.0334	AAPL	1
-0.19	-0.2998	-0.0778	-0.3652	-0.2131	-0.037	MSFT	1
0.2211	0.3495	0.0127	0.0821	-0.1544	0.0146	MSFT	1
1.5646	2.1532	0.2961	6.1212	-0.0484	0.1201	MSFT	1
1.336	1.9815	0.2256	4.6636	-0.0484	0.1026	SPY	1
-1.186	-1.8741	-0.1773	-1.1571	-0.1533	-0.0909	SPY	1